

Survey of Tetracycline Residue in Egg from Commercial Farm and Households in Sokoto Metropolis, Sokoto State Northwestern Nigeria

¹Umar Abubakar Alhaji, ²Dahiru Abdu, ¹Nuhu Hussaini Shehu, ²Shehu Aliyu, ³Saulawa Mahmud Abdullahi, Gali Abaka Umaru and ⁴Sidi Shehu

¹Ministry of Animal Health, Husbandry and Fisheries, Kebbi State

²Department of Veterinary and Pest Control Services Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security, Nigeria

²Ministry of Animal Health and Fisheries Development, Sokoto State

³Department of Veterinary Public Health and Preventive Medicine, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Bayero University Kano, Kano State

⁴Department of Theriogenology and Animal Production, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Sokoto State

Received 15 July, 2023, Accepted 20 August, 2023, Published 9 December 2023

This study was designed to detect and quantify the presence of tetracycline residues from eggs in commercial farms and households in Sokoto metropolis. Out of the 160 eggs sampled (54 exotic chickens eggs, 53 indigenous chickens eggs and guinea fowls eggs) and analyzed for tetracycline residues using competitive enzyme linked immunosorbent assay, an overall detection rate of 40.6% (65/160) was recorded. Exotic chicken eggs had a detection rate of 48.1% (26/54), Indigenous chicken eggs had detection rate of 34.0% (18/53) and guinea fowls had detection rate of 39.6% (21/53). Chi-square analysis showed no statistical significant association between tetracycline residues detected and type of eggs sampled $P > 0.05$. Mann Whitney U test showed an overall statistical significant difference in the mean concentration of tetracycline residues $P < 0.05$. From the questionnaire survey an overall percentage of poultry farmers that use tetracycline in their poultry were 67.5% (108/160). It was concluded that eggs from commercial farms and households had tetracycline residues below the maximum residue limit. This necessitated the need carry out tetracycline detection and quantification throughout the entire state. Government should establish tetracycline and other antibiotic residues enlightenment, monitoring and surveillance programmes within the state.

Keywords: Eggs, Poultry, Oxytetracycline, Residue, Survey, Sokoto State

INTRODUCTION

Antibiotic is any class of organic molecule that inhibits or kill microbes by specific interactions with bacterial targets without any consideration of the source of the particular compound or class (Waksman, 1973). Thus purely synthetic therapeutics are considered antibiotics. They can be applied parentally, orally or topically (Geidam *et*

al., 2009), and are among the most widely used veterinary drugs in poultry industry (Simon and Baxter, 2006). The frequent use of antibiotics in clinical practice causes the occurrence of antibiotic residues in various food products of animal origin including milk, egg, and meat. Presence of drug or antibiotic residues in food above the maximum acceptable level has been recognized worldwide by various public authorities (Kempe and Verachtert, 2000). It is almost impossible to produce food of animal origin which is completely free from traces of drugs or chemicals (Campbell, 1978).

*Corresponding author's e-mail:
abualhajizagga2014@yahoo.com

Nowadays, antibiotics are used on a large scale in poultry farms to cure or prevent diseases and promote growth. The irrational use of drugs leads to accumulation of residues that consist of the parent compound or compounds derived from the parent drug (or both), including metabolites, conjugates and residues bound to macromolecules. Residues appeared in human food of animal origin and certain greatly affected the life and health of human causing allergic phenomena, sensitization, teratogenic, carcinogenic effects and antibiotic resistance (Mitchell *et al.*, 1998). Antibiotics are used by the poultry industry and poultry veterinarians to enhance growth and feed efficiency and reduce disease. Antibiotic usage has facilitated the efficient production of poultry, allowing the consumer to purchase, at a reasonable cost, high quality meat and eggs. Antibiotic usage has also enhanced the health and well-being of poultry by reducing the incidence of disease. Although these uses benefit all involved, unfortunately, consumer perceptions are that edible poultry tissues are contaminated with harmful concentrations of drug residues (Donoghue, 2003).

In Nigeria, a large population of poultry is held by the so-called backyard poultry farmers who readily have access to veterinary drugs and always purchase drugs over the counter for administration without veterinary prescription and supervision. This results in indiscriminate use of these drugs especially in food animals (Dipeolu, 2004). Consequently, the inappropriate use and handling of these antibiotics has led to occurrence of harmful residues in edible poultry tissues (meat and eggs) and other animal products like milk (Olatoye and Ehinmowo, 2009; Shareef *et al.*, 2009). There has also been long standing report of genetically determined renal tubular functional defect due to consumption of degraded tetracycline (Gross, 1963). As a result of reported occurrences in different parts of the world, coupled with low awareness reported in the developing world, the World Health Organization encourages effective reporting of drug residues in foods of animal origin destined for human consumption (WHO, 2004). Antimicrobial drug residues have been demonstrated to be present in tissues of food animals and their respective by-products in different parts of Nigeria (Dipeolu *et al.*, 2000; Dipeolu and Ayinde 2001, Kabir *et al.*, 2004). Tetracyclines were first discovered in 1945 (Duggar, 1948). Chlortetracycline and oxytetracycline were produced by *Streptomyces aureofaciens* and *S. rimosus* respectively. Semisynthetic tetracyclines were developed, e.g. methacycline, doxycycline, minocycline, rolitetracycline, lymecycline and the most recently produced glycylicyclines (Goldstein *et al.*, 1994). They were the first major group of antibiotics to which the term "broad-spectrum" was ascribed (Roberts, 1997).

Today, antimicrobial drugs are used to control, prevent, and treat infections and to enhance animal growth and

feed conversion efficiency (Tollefson and Miller, 2000). Currently, approximately 80% of all food-producing animals receive medication for part or most of their lives; the most commonly used antimicrobials in food producing animals are the β -lactams, tetracyclines, aminoglycosides, lincosamides, macrolides, pleuromutilins, and sulfonamides (Lee *et al.*, 2001). Antibiotic residues in foods of animal origin may be the cause of numerous health concerns in humans. These problems include toxic effects, transfer of antibiotic resistant bacteria to humans, immunopathological effects, carcinogenicity (e.g., sulphamethazine, oxytetracycline, and furazolidone), mutagenicity, nephropathy (e.g., gentamicin), hepatotoxicity, reproductive disorders, bone marrow toxicity (e.g., chloramphenicol), and allergy (e.g., penicillin) (Nisha, 2008). The need to meet up with the demand for poultry meat has necessitated the large scale production of poultry and subsequent use of veterinary drugs, especially antimicrobials (Dipeolu and Alonge, 2002). These antimicrobials are particularly used in poultry farming for therapeutic purposes and are added in feed and water in sub-therapeutic doses for prophylaxis and growth promotion (Dipeolu and Alonge, 2002). They tend to accumulate in tissues and organs to form residues at different concentrations. Antimicrobial residues were reported by Fagbamila *et al.* (2010) in commercial eggs from thirty commercial layer farms in Plateau; of the 900 commercial eggs screened, 3.6% tested positive for antimicrobial residues.

Residues of antibiotics of the tetracycline group were detected in 7% local egg, 25% in commercial egg, 5% in boiled local egg, and 24% in boiled commercial egg samples in Bangladesh as tested using Microbial inhibition test (MIT), (Suchayan *et al.*, 2012). From total of 60 samples tested by the Four-plate test (FPT) 18 (30%) cases were diagnosed to be contaminated with antibiotic residues, 11 (61.11%) cases were relevant to macrolides, 4 (22.22%) cases were relevant to aminoglycosides and 3 (16.66%) cases were relevant to tetracycline (Mohammad *et al.*, 2014). When egg samples were tested by High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), 50% of the samples collected from Buraydah contained tetracycline. From Oneizah, Saudi Arabia, only two samples contained tetracycline in Qassim (Naser *et al.*, 2011).

There are ethical and professional concerns as to the safety of the public from drug-residue related diseases and the development of antibiotic resistant pathogenic microorganisms (Al-Nazawi 2006; Hassan *et al.*, 2007; Khaniki 2007). The occurrence of antimicrobial residues is a serious poultry farm problem in Nigeria due to non-compliance with guidelines and recommendations on antimicrobial use and Lack of drug monitoring programme in the country is leading to the build-up of antimicrobial residues in eggs (Fagbamila *et al.*, 2012). Consumption of antibiotic residues could result in public health hazards including: development of resistant strains

of micro-organisms, hypersensitive reactions in sensitised individuals (Vollard and Clasener, 1994., Nisha, 2008), and Distortion of intestinal micro flora (Cunha, 2001).

Eggs form part of primary source of diet in young and young adult individuals in Sokoto metropolis. There is limited information on tetracycline residues in marketed eggs from commercial farms and households in Sokoto metropolis, as well as paucity of information on the current status of tetracycline residues in eggs from commercial farms and households in Sokoto metropolis. As a result, it is of paramount importance to create awareness assess and quantify tetracycline residues in eggs from exotic, indigenous and guinea fowl poultry in Sokoto metropolis. The study will help legislative and policy makers in designing effective control and prevention strategies, if the residues are detected in Sokoto metropolis.

Research Questions

Are there tetracycline residues in eggs from exotic poultry and from indigenous poultry (chickens and guinea fowls) in Sokoto metropolis?

Are poultry producers in Sokoto metropolis aware of presence of drug residues in poultry products?

Are there differences in concentration of tetracycline residues in eggs from exotic, indigenous and guinea fowl poultry?

The aim of the study is to detect the presence of tetracycline residues in eggs from exotic and indigenous poultry in Sokoto metropolis. The objectives of the research are:

To determine the presence or absence of tetracycline residues in eggs from exotic poultry and from indigenous poultry (chickens and guinea fowls) in commercial farms and households in Sokoto metropolis using quantitative ELISA technique

To compare the presence of tetracycline residues in eggs from exotic poultry and from indigenous poultry (chickens and guinea fowls) in the study area

To determine the level of use of antibiotics from commercial farms and households in the study area

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

Sokoto is the capital of Sokoto state which is located in the northwestern part of Nigeria between longitudes $4^{\circ} 8'$ E and $6^{\circ} 54'$ E and latitudes 12° N and $13^{\circ} 58'$ N. It forms borders with Republic of Niger to the north; Kebbi State to the west and southwest, and Zamfara State to the east. Sokoto metropolis constitutes the local government

areas of Sokoto North, Sokoto South, Wamakko, Kware and Dange-Shuni. The state is divided into 23 local government areas (L.G.As). Farming is the mainstay of the people's economy accounting for a significant proportion of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and responsible for about 70% of the total employment (NPC, 1991). Sokoto state ranks second in the nation in livestock population with estimated 3 million cattle, 3 million sheep, 5 million goats, 4,600 camels (Mocit, 2002) and 2 million chickens (NRDP, 2003).

Research design

The study was a cross sectional survey

Sample Size Determination

The minimum sample size was determined using the

$$n = \frac{t^2 \cdot p \cdot (1-p)}{d^2}$$

formula: d^2 (Thrusfield, 2010)

where

n= sample size

t= 1.96 at 95% confidence interval p= previous prevalence

d= allowable error of estimation (5%)

p had been estimated to be 3.6% based on prevalence reported by Fagbamila *et. al* (2010).

$$s = (1.96^2) \times 0.036 (1-0.036) / (0.05)^2$$

$$s = 3.8416 \times 0.036 \times 0.964 / 0.0025 \quad s = 0.133 / 0.0025$$

$$= 53 \text{ eggs for each sample}$$

A total of 160 eggs, 54 from exotic layers, 53 from indigenous chickens and 53 from guinea fowl were conveniently sampled in 2 weeks in Sokoto metropolis.

For eggs from exotic layer farm, 11 eggs from Sokoto South, 11 eggs from Wamakko, 11 eggs from Kware, 11 eggs from Dange Shuni and 10 eggs from Sokoto North were collected from different farms.

For eggs from indigenous chickens, 11 eggs from Sokoto South, 11 eggs from Wamakko, 10 eggs from Kware, 11 eggs from Dange Shuni and 10 eggs from Sokoto North were collected from different households.

For eggs from guinea fowl, 11 eggs from Sokoto South, 11 eggs from Wamakko, 10 eggs from Kware, 11 eggs from Dange Shuni and 10 eggs from Sokoto North were collected from different households which were all placed in labeled transparent polythene bags and transported to the Veterinary Central Research Laboratory, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto and stored at 4°C until the time of analysis, in which europroxima 5091TC test kit was used.

Clinical questionnaire was administered to commercial farms and households as egg samples were collected to find out information on drugs used in the treatment of common diseases that affect poultry in the study area.

Sample preparation

Egg sample was homogenized with the aid of pestle and mortar, one gram of homogenized egg sample was poured into 15ml plastic tubes, three ml of McIlvain buffer pH 7 (1:1 diluted with methanol) was added which was vortexed rigorously and mixed head-over-head for 10 minutes. Immediately after the sample was centrifuged at 2000xg for 10 minutes, after that 50 μ l of the supernatant was pipetted into a new tube and 200 μ l of dilution buffer added, 50 μ l of this preparation was used in the tetracycline ELISA microtiter plate wells

Preparation of reagent

Before beginning the test, the reagents were brought up to ambient temperature. Any reagent not used was placed back into storage immediately at +2°C to +8°C.

Dilution buffer

Dilution buffer no. 1 is 4x concentrated. The buffer was diluted 1:4 (1 ml buffer + 3 ml distilled water) before use. The buffer is for dissolving conjugate and to prepare the sample dilution buffer.

Sample dilution buffer

Sample dilution buffer was prepared by adding 18 ml dilution buffer to 2 ml 100% methanol which was stored at 4°C until use.

McIlvain buffer

McIlvain buffer was prepared by adding 0.2 M Sodium dibasic solution (Na_2HPO_4 28.4 g) + 1 liter of distilled water, 0.1 M Trisodium citrate dehydrate solution ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7\text{Na}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 29.4 g) + 1 liter of distilled water. The two solutions were mixed at ratio 1:1 the pH was adjusted to 7.0 with HCL, finally the solution was diluted with methanol at ratio 1:1 before use.

Standard 2 ng/ml

Dilution range of tetracycline standard was prepared and added to 2 ml of sample dilution buffer to the tetracycline standard and mixed. The solution contains 2 ng tetracycline per ml. 0.25ml of the solution was pipetted into a clean tube and added to 0.25 ml of sample dilution buffer, continued to make a dilution range of 1.0, 0.5, 0.25, 0.125 and 0.625ng/ml.

Standard 1000 ng/ml

One ml of the sample dilution was added to tetracycline standard and mixed. The solution contains 1000 ng tetracycline per ml.

Conjugate

The vial of lyophilized conjugate (tetracycline – HRP) was reconstituted with 6 ml of dilution buffer mixed thoroughly and kept in a dark place until use.

Rinsing buffer

The rinsing buffer was delivered 20 times concentrated. Dilutions were prepared freshly before use. For each strip 40 ml of diluted rinsing buffer was used (2 ml concentrated rinsing buffer + 38 ml distilled water).

Substrate/chromogen solution

The substrate/chromogen solution (ready to use) tends to precipitate at + 4°C. care was taken that the vial is at room temperature before use and the content was mixed before pipetting into microtiter wells.

ASSAY PROCEDURE

Rinsing protocol

In ELISA, between each immunological incubation step, unbound components have to be removed efficiently. This was reached by appropriate rinsing. Each rinsing procedure was carried out with care to guarantee good inter – and intra – assay results. Basically, manual rinsing was performed as follows:

Manual rinsing

- The content of each well was emptied by turning the microtiter plate upside down and residual liquid was removed by striking the plate against a paper towel.
- All the wells were filled to the rims (300 μ l) with rinsing solution.
- This rinsing cycle (1 and 2) was carried out 3 times
- The plate was turned upside down and emptied the wells by a firm short vertical movement
- The inverted plate was placed on adsorbent paper towels and tapped the plate firmly to remove residual washing solution from the wells
- Care was taken that none of the wells dry out before the next reagent is dispensed

Assay protocol

Hundred μ l of the sample dilution buffer was pipetted in duplicate (wells H1, H2, blank). 50 μ l of the sample dilution buffer (zero standard, Bmax) was pipetted in duplicate (wells A1, A2). 50 μ l of each of the standard solutions in duplicate (wells B1, 2 to G1, 2 i.e. 0.0625, 0.125, 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 ng/ml), 50 μ l of each sample solution was pipetted into the remaining wells of the microtiter plate, 50 μ l of conjugate (tetracycline -HRP) was pipetted to all wells, except H1 and H2. The microtiter plate was sealed and shaken for few seconds on a microtiter plate shaker, after that the plate is incubated for 1 hour in the dark at room temperature (20°C to 25°C), the solution was discarded from the

FIGURE 4.1.1: Total number of eggs sampled

FIGURE 4.1.2: Detection rate of tetracycline residues in exotic eggs, indigenous eggs and guinea fowl eggs in percentage (%).

microtiter plate and washed 3 times with rinsing buffer. One hundred µl of substrate solution was pipetted into each well, which was incubated 30 minutes in dark at room temperature (20°C to 25°C), 100 µl of stop solution was added to each well, and finally the reading of the adsorbance value is done immediately at 450nm (www.europroxima.com).

Data presentation and analysis

The data obtained from this study were subjected to descriptive statistics (Tables and charts), Non-parametric test (Chi-squared was used for the samples that were positive, Asymptomatic Mann-Whitney test was applied to residues in eggs from exotic poultry eggs, indigenous chicken eggs and guinea fowl eggs to evaluate possible differences). Descriptive statistics was carried out using

Microsoft excel 2007, Non-parametric test was carried out using INVIVOSTAT (version 3.0.0.0, 2008-2015).

RESULTS

Frequency of eggs sampled and out come

A total of 160 eggs were sampled from five local governments which constitutes Sokoto metropolis (Sokoto south, Sokoto north, Kware, Wamakko and Dange shuni). Number of eggs sampled from each type of poultry is given in Table I Fifty-four 54 out of all the eggs sampled were from exotic poultry, fifty-three 53 were from indigenous chickens and fifty-three 53 were from guinea fowl. Detection rate for each type of eggs is given in Table II. The highest detection rate for

Table I Number of eggs sampled from each type of poultry

Type of poultry eggs	No. of eggs tested
Exotic	54
Indigenous	53
Guinea fowl	53
Total	160

Table II Detection rate for exotic eggs, indigenous eggs and guinea fowl eggs in percentage (%)

Type of poultry eggs	No. tested	No. positive (%)	No. negative (%)
Exotic	54	26 (48.1)	28 (51.8)
Indigenous	53	18 (33.9)	35 (66)
Guinea fowl	53	21 (39.6)	32 (60.4)
Total	160	65 (121.6)	95 (178.2)
$X^2 = 2.26$	$P\text{-value} = 0.3223$		$p > 0.05$

Table III. Concentrations of tetracycline residues in eggs from exotic, indigenous and guinea fowl poultry in part per billion (ppb).

S/N	Exotic	Indigenous	Guinea Fowl
1	7.835	3.229	5.267
2	5.67	6.976	3.243
3	8.055	54.826	5.25
4	56.379	20.218	22.374
5	4.313	22.152	5.165
6	5.688	4.514	0.286
7	7.791	20.237	0.256
8	2.873	0.695	0.885
9	5.886	0.927	3.866
10	40.44	0.868	3.285
11		0.271	1.767
12		2.918	3.053
13		0.252	14.349
14		0.283	15.755
15		21.702	4.09
16		0.317	2.133
17		4.945	2.868
18		1.614	1.978

Table IV Mean concentration

Type	Exotic	Indigenous	Guinea fowl
Mean conc.	19.57±7.04	8.96± 3.15	5.09 ± 1.21
P. value	0.0178		
Post Hoc	AsMW test		
Exotic vs. indigenous	P. value		0.0181
Exotic vs. guinea fowl			0.0008
Indigenous vs. guinea fowl			0.7761

tetracycline was from exotic poultry eggs with occurrence of 26 (48.1%) and was followed guinea fowl eggs with 21 (39.6%) then by indigenous chicken eggs with 18 (33.9%).

Questionnaire survey

From the questionnaire survey, 160 of the questionnaire

administered to farmers were returned representing a total of 100% responses. The status on use of drugs showed that 44 (27.5%) of the respondent's poultry were been treated by owners, 35 (21.8%) by veterinarians, 11(6.9%) by animal attendants, 1(0.6%) by farm managers and 7(4.4%) by others. On the knowledge of antibiotics 116 (72.5%) are aware of antibiotics, while 39 (24.4%) are not aware of antibiotics, 74(46.3%) knows

tetracycline related drugs, 6(3.8%) do not, 51(31.9%) knows both tetracycline related and non-tetracycline related drugs, 112 (70%) knows tetracycline while 46 (28.8%) do not know, 40 (25%) knows that tetracycline is used for prevention and treatment of diseases, 16 (10%) knows that tetracycline is used for prevention of diseases, while 59 (36.8%) knows that it is used for treatment only, 95 (59.4%) of the respondents use tetracycline on their poultry, 62 (38.8%) did not use it on their poultry, 4(2.5%) administer tetracycline to their poultry through feed while 92 (57.5%) administer it through drinking water, 84 (52.5%) uses tetracycline within a week 0-7days 10(6.3%) uses it 7-14 days while 1(0.6%) use it in 14-21 days, on the frequency of use of tetracycline 36(22.5%) use it once in their poultry, 23 (14.4%) use it twice, 19(11.9%) use it trice and 18(11.3%) use it several times, 67(41.9%) use tetracycline below a month while 28 (17.5%) above a month, 6(3.7%) of the farmers had their feed containing tetracycline while 154(96.3%) did not, however 61(38.2%) of the farmers are aware of withdrawal period while 99 (61.8%) of them are not, only 50(31.3%) of the farmers adhere to withdrawal period while 110 (68.7%) don't do so.

DISCUSSION

Available data suggests that antimicrobial residues may be present in a large proportion of poultry products in developing countries, especially in Africa, the Middle East and South America. Al-Ghamdi *et al.* (2000) who used high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method, reported an antimicrobial residue detection rate of 60% in eggs sampled from the eastern province of Saudi Arabia; Nonga *et al.* (2009) carried out a study to assess antimicrobial residues in commercial chicken eggs in Morogoro Municipality in Tanzania reported that all eggs sampled (70 eggs) and analyzed with Delvo test kit were positive for antimicrobial residues.

Routine detection of tetracycline residues in eggs in Nigeria is not adequate, reports on. Detection rate of tetracycline residues are mostly in poultry meat. Thus, the real detection rate of tetracycline residues in eggs and their concentration in the country is largely unknown. This study, shows detection rate of tetracycline residues and concentration in eggs of different poultry (exotic, chicken and guinea fowl).

The detection rate of 48.1%, 33.9% and 39.6% were recorded from exotic eggs, local chicken eggs and guinea fowl eggs respectively in this study, it was higher than the 3.6% (n= 900) reported by Fagbamila *et al.*, (2010). The difference in detection rate may be due to the different type of diagnostic method used because in the previous report, it was based on disc diffusion test which utilizes the genus *bacillus* because it detect majority of antibiotics which cannot be used to identify individual antibiotics,

therefore a positive result should be confirmed with chemical physical method (Kirbis, 2006; Javadi *et al.*, 2009).

While in this study it was Europroxima® ELISA test kit that is specifically meant for the detection of tetracycline residues with a specificity and sensitivity of 100%. However, the sample type may also affect the detection rate; in this research the sample type is convenient while Fagbamila *et al.*, (2010) employ stratified random sampling method.

Thus the detection rate obtained in this study was most likely as a result of increase in wide use of tetracycline among poultry farmers for different purposes; treatment, prevention and control of diseases and as growth promoters in poultry (Dipeolu *et al.*, 2004; Pavlov *et al.*, 2008). Wambeke, (2010) reported a detection rate of 76% following High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method of analysis of tetracycline residues in eggs and broiler meat and its application to a feeding trial which is higher than this study which may be attributed to the difference in method of analysis bearing that HPLC is the gold standard for detection of antibiotic residues.

Also the difference may be as a result of sample size used in this study which is lower than the one previously reported. Sirdar, (2008). Reported a detection rate of antibiotics on average of 63% in layer farms using growth inhibition of *Geobacillus stearothermophilus var. calidolactis* in-house test from Khartoum state, Sudan; Hind, (2012) also recorded detection rate of 49.6% and 12.7% in eggs using Disc assay and Premi® test methods respectively. Kehinde, (2012) recorded 62.5% using Premi® test; a study conducted in Nigeria (Kabir *et al.*, 2004) found antimicrobial residues in 1% of the eggs sampled (200 eggs) using disc diffusion microbial inhibition test with *Bacillus cereus* and *Micrococcus luteus*.

In Sokoto metropolis, Sokoto, Nigeria exotic Poultry are mainly kept by Commercial farms usually for commercial purpose; local chicken and guinea fowls are mainly kept by backyard or house holding farmers who rear them for domestic consumption majorly which eventually allows them to buy drugs from vendors and administer at any particular time leading to irrational use of drugs which may eventually leads to accumulation of drug residues in meat and eggs of their origin.

In Sokoto, Nigeria reports on detection rate of tetracycline residues using Europroxima® ELISA test kit in eggs was not available prior to this study. Irrational use of antibiotics is one of the major problems related to the presence of antibiotic residues in animal products (Mitchell *et al.*, 1998).

CONCLUSION

The study has established the presence of tetracycline residues in eggs from exotic poultry, indigenous chickens

and guinea fowls within Sokoto metropolis. The disease status of poultry and the way tetracycline are administered to poultry influence the potentials for tetracycline residues. This study showed that poultry farmers in Sokoto metropolis were not adhering to the withdrawal period of tetracycline are unintentionally allowing the accumulation of tetracycline residues in eggs. This is not a surprise because there has little or no monitoring programme put in place by government neither has there been compulsory effort to sensitize the people on the dangers associated with tetracycline residues in eggs. As poultry farming increases there is increase in use of tetracycline because poultry farmers are more likely to take measures towards minimizing financial losses resulting from mortality on their poultry such as prophylactic and therapeutic use of tetracycline.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations are made.

1. Farmers should adhere to rational administration of tetracycline to their poultry.
2. Government should establish a monitoring and surveillance programme on tetracycline residues.
3. Government should establish public enlightenment programme on tetracycline residues through veterinarians.
4. The enforcement of laws for every farm with up to 200 birds and veterinary drug sellers to register with the state veterinary services which help in the regulation of tetracycline supply and irrational use.
5. More researches need to be conducted on tetracycline residues within the entire state.

REFERENCES

- Agwuh N.K. and MacGowan A. (2006). Pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of the tetracyclines including glycylicyclines. *J. Antimicrobial Chemotherapy* 58: 256-265.
- AHI (2002): Survey shows decline in antibiotic use in animals. (Animal Health Institute) <http://www.ahi.org/mediaCenter/pressReleases/surveyShowsDecline.asp> 29-04-16, 6:02 pm.
- AISLP (2003) Summary of product characteristics. <https://www.klinickafarmakologie.cz/pdfs/far/2003/01/02> 11:02pm
- Al-Ghamdi, M., Al-Mustapha, Z., El-Morsy, F., Al-Facky, A., Haider, I., and Essa. (2000). Residues of tetracycline compounds in poultry products in the eastern province of Saudi Arabia. *J. Public Health*. 114 300-304
- Al-Nazawi M.H. (2006). Resistance and residues of antibacterial in dairy farm and dairy production in Al-Hassa region. *Saudi Arabian J. Medical Sci.* 6: 198-202.
- Al-Mazeedi, H. M., Abbas, B.A., Alomirah, H.F., Al-Joutiar, W.Y., Al-musty (2009). Screening for tetracycline residues in food products of animal origin in the State of Kuwait using Charm II radio-immunoassay and LC/MS/MS methods, *Food Additives and Contaminants* 1-11, iFirst.
- Al-Wabel, N.A. (2011). Monitoring of tetracycline residues in table eggs collected from Qassim Region, KSA. *J. Agric. and Vet. Sci.* Qassim University, 4(2): 109-123.
- Boatman (1998). Survey of antimicrobial usage in animal health in the European Union. Boatman Consulting, by order of (European Federation for Animal Health). Europe .85-95
- Booth N.H. (1988). Toxicology of drugs and chemical residues. In: *Veterinary Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, Booth, N.H. and McDonald, L.E (eds) 6th edition. Iowa State University Press/Ames. Pp. 1149-1205.
- Botsoglov N.A., Fletouris (2001). Drug residues in foods. *Pharmacology, food safety and analysis*. 1st edition, New York Marcel Dekker.94-101.
- Campbell DJ. (1978). Drug residue in animal tissues and their regulatory significance the Canadian point of view. *Association of Official Analytical Chemists* 61(5): 1194 - 1197.
- Chowdhury S., Hassan, M.M., Alam, S., Bari, M.S., Saifuddin, A.K.M. and Houque, M.A. (2015). Antibiotic residues in milk and eggs of commercial and local farms at Chittagong, Bangladesh. *Vet. World*. 8(4):467-471
- Cook W.R. (1973). Diarrhea in the horse associated with stress and tetracycline therapy. *Vet. Record* . 93, 15.
- Dang Pharm Kim *et al.*, (2013). Preliminary evaluation of antimicrobial residue levels in marketed pork and chicken meat in the red river. Delta region of Vietnam. *J. Food and Public Health*.3 (6): 267-276.
- Cunha B.A. (2001). Antibiotics side effects. *Medical Clinics of North America*, 85, 149-185
- Dipeolu, M.A., Akpan N.J. and Olutayo A. (2000). Tetracycline residues in commercial eggs and turkey meat sold for human consumption. *Nig. Poultry Sci. J.* 1: 4-11.
- Dipeolu M.A. and Ayinde A.A. (2001). Investigation of marketed pork for tetracycline residues. *Nigerian Veterinary Journal*. 22: 84-86.
- Dipeolu, M.A. and Alonge, D.O. (2002). Residues of streptomycin antibiotic in meat sold for human consumption in some States of SW Nigeria. *Archivos de Zootecnia* 51, 477-480.
- Dipeolu M.A. (2004). Problems and prospects of antibiotics residues in meat products in Nigeria. *Vom J. Vet. Sci.* 1(1): 63-67.
- Donoghue DJ. (2000). Myers K. Imaging residue transfer into egg yolks. *J. Agric. Food Chemicals*. 48:6428-6430.
- Donoghue DJ. (2001). Mechanisms regulating drug and pesticide residue uptake by egg yolks: development of predictive models. *World Poultry Sci. J.* 57:373-380. 6.
- Donoghue DJ. (2003). Antibiotic residues In poultry tissues and eggs: Human health concerns. *Poultry Sci. J.* 82:618-621
- Droumev, D. (1983). Review of antimicrobial growth promoting agents. *Vet. Res. Communications*.7: 85-99
- Duggar B.M. (1948). A product of the continuing search for new antibiotics. *Annals of the New York Academy of Science*. 51, 177-181
- Dupont H.L., Steele J.H. (1987): The human health implications of the use of antimicrobial agents in animal feeds. *Vet. Quarterly*. 9, 309-320.
- EEC 70/ 524 (1970). Concerning additives in feeding-stuffs. Northern Europe. 1-38. 07-07-17, 6: 47 pm.
- EC (2010). Commission staff working document on the implementation of national residue monitoring plans in the member states in 2009 [European Commission \(EC\) Council Directive. https://www.omicsonline.org/./veterinary-drug-residues-in-foodanimal-products_07-07-17_11:23](https://www.omicsonline.org/./veterinary-drug-residues-in-foodanimal-products_07-07-17_11:23) pm.
- EMA (1999). Antibiotic Resistance in the European Union Associated with Therapeutic use of Veterinary Medicines. Report and Qualitative Risk Assessment by the Committee for Veterinary Medicinal Products. (The European Agency for the Evaluation of Medicinal Products) <http://www.emea.eu.int/pdfs/vet/regaffair/034299ENC.pdf> 05-09-16, 12: 00 pm.
- Fagbamila I. O., Kabir J, Abdu P, Omeiza G, Ankeli P, Ngulukun S, Muhammad M. and Umoh J. (2010). Antimicrobial screening of commercial eggs and determination of tetracycline residue using two microbiological methods. *Int. J. Poultry Sci.* 10: 959.
- Fagbamila I.O., Ngulukun S.S., Ardzard S.S., Sati N., Ajayi O.T, Ankeli, Y. Akalusi P.I., Okeke L., Ikpa L., Odugbo M.O. and Muhammad M., (2012). Validation of commercial test kit for microbiological screening

- of antimicrobials in chicken Eggs. *Res. J. Vet. Sci.* 5: 75-80.
- FAO (2008). Food and agricultural organization of the United Nation. Food outlook market analysis; meat and meat products prices. Coporate document repository, Italy. www.fao.org/docrep/010/ai466e/ai466e08.htm_17-07-17, 12: am.
- FAO/WHO (1990). Evaluation of certain veterinary drug residues in food. Fiftieth report of joint FAO/WHO expert committee on food additives. *World Health Organization Technical report.* 1-95
- Fritz J.W., Zuo Y. (2007). Simultaneous determination of tetracycline, oxytetracycline and 4-epitetracycline in milk by High Performance Liquid Chromatography. *J. Food Chemistry.* 105:1297-1301
- Gaudin V, Hedou C, Rault A, Sanders P, Verdon E. (2009). Comparative study of three screening tests, two microbiological tube tests and a multi-sulphonamide Elisa kit for the detection of antimicrobial residues in eggs. *Food Additives and Contaminant.* A26: 427-440
- Geidam, Y.A., H. Usman, H.I. Musa, F. Anosike and Y. Adeyemi, (2009). Ox tetracycline and Procain Penicillin residues in tissues of slaughtered cattle in Maiduguri, Borno state, Nigeria. *Int. J. Animal and Vet. Advances.* 3(2): 68-70.
- Goldstein F.W., Kitzis M.D., Acar J.F. (1994). N,N-dimethyl glycol amino derivative of minocycline and 6-demethyl-6-desoxytetracycline, two new glycolcyclines, highly effective against tetracycline-resistant Gram-positive cocci. *Antimicrobial Agents Chemotherapy.* 38, 2218-2220.
- Gross, J.M., (1963). Fanconi syndrome (adult type) developing secondary to ingestion of out-dated tetracycline. *Annals of Internal Med.* 58: 523-528.
- Gustafson, R. (1993). Historical perspectives on regulatory issues of antimicrobial resistance. *Vet. Human Toxicol.* 35: 2-5.
- Gyrd-Hansen, N., Rasmussen Fand Smith M. (1981). Cardiovascular effects of intravenous administration of tetracycline in cattle. *J. Vet. Pharmacol. and Therapeutics.* 4: 15-21.
- Harry, W., Levis and Christopher, J. Moody (1989). Experimental organic chemistry. *Principles and Practice Illustrated Edition.* WilleyBlackwell. Pp 159-173 ISBN 978-0-632-02017-1.
- Hind A. (2012). Detection of antibiotic residues in table eggs using disc assay and premi test in Khartoum State, Sudan. *Journal of Veterinary Medicine and Animal Production.* 3 (2) 16-27.
- Hinton et al. (1985). Antibiotic use in animal feed and its impact on human health. *Nutrition Society Cambridge.* 13:2 pp 279-299.
- Hussein, K Marcinak S, Mated K, Sokol J, and Zdolec N. (2005). Use of premi test for detection of sulphonamide residues in chicken eggs. *Acta veterinaria* (Beograd) 55:493-500.
- Immelman A., Botha W.S., Grib D. (1978): Muscle irritation caused by different products containing oxytetracycline. *J. South Afri. Vet. Association.* 49, 103-105.
- IOM (Institute of Medicine) Division of Health Promotion and Disease Prevention (1998): Report of a study: Human health risks with the subtherapeutic use of penicillin or tetracyclines in animal feed. *National Academy Press, Washington, D.C.*
- Jackson, B. A (1980). Toxicology of drug and chemical residues. In *Veterinary Pharmacology and Therapeutics* 6th Edition. 1988 (Booth, N.H And Mcdonald, L.E.,Eds). Iowa State University Press. Ames, Pp 1149-51
- Javadi A., H. Mirzaei and S.A. Khatibi. (2009). Effect of roasting process on antibiotic residues in edible tissues of poultry by FRT method. *J. Animal Vet. Advances.* 8 (12) 2468-2472.
- Jetacar, (1999). Antibiotic growth-promoters in food animals. *Division of Microbiology United Kingdom.*
- Jollef et al. (1956). Diagnosis and treatment of nutritional disturbances. *American J. Digestive Diseases.* 1:8 ISSN 0002-9211.
- Kabir, J.,Umoh V.J., Audu-Okoha E. Umoh J.U and Kwaga, J.K.P. (2004). Veterinary drug use in poultry farms and determination of antimicrobial drug residues in commercial eggs and slaughtered chicken in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Food Control.* 15: 99-105.
- Kehinde G. O. (2012). Detection of antimicrobial drug residues in commercial eggs using premi test. *Internation Journal of Poultry Science.* 11 (1) 50-54
- Kempe, M. and Verachtert, B. (2000) Cartridges with molecularly imprinted recognition elements for antibiotic residues monitoring in milk cream pure and applied biochemistry. *Lunds University Centre for Chemistry and Chemical Engineering Getingeaven, Lund, Sweden.* p1-10.
- Khaniki, G.R.J., (2007). Chemical contaminants in milk and public health concerns: A review. *Int. J. Dairy Sci.* 2: 104-115.
- Kirbis, A. (2006). Microbiological 5 plate screening method for detection of tetracyclines, aminoglycosides, cephalosporins and macrolides in milk. *Slovenian Vet. Res.* 43 (4) 161-168
- Langlois et al. (1984). The effects of feeding (45 days) therapeutic and subtherapeutic quantities of tetracycline and different therapeutic doses of oxytetracycline (3 daily doses) were compared. *Journal of Animal Science* 58 (3) 666-674.
- Lee, H. J., Lee, M. H. and Ruy, P. D. (2001). Public health risks: chemical and antibiotic residues. *Asian-Australian Journal of Animal Science.*, 14: 402- 413.
- Levy, S.B. (1992). *The Antibiotic Paradox: How the Miracle Drugs Are Destroying the Miracle.* Plenum Press, N.Y. *Veterinary Medicine.-Czech,* 49, 2004 (3): 79-100
- Mitchell JM, Griffiths MW, McEwen SA, Mcab W, Yee AJ. (1998) Antimicrobial drug residues in milk and meat: causes, concerns, prevalence, regulations, tests and test performance. *Journal of Food Protection.* 61(6): 742-756.
- MOCIT, (2002). <http://www.aiol.info/index.php/article/viewfile/85551/75480>. 29-04-16, 5:57 pm.
- Moellerling R.C. (1990). Principles of anti-effective therapy. In: Mendel G.L., Douglas R.G., Bennet J.E. (eds.): *Principles and Practice of Infectious Disease.* Churchill Livingstone Inc., N.Y. Pp. 206-218.
- Moffit J.M., Cooley R.O., Olsen N.H. (1974): Prediction of tetracycline-induced teeth discoloration. *Journal of American Dental Association .,* 88, 547-552 .
- Navratilova P., Borkova I., Drackova M., Janstova B., Vorlava L.(2009).Occurance of tetracycline, chlortetracycline and oxyteracycline residues in row milk. *Czech Journal of Food Science.* 27:379-385
- Nisha A. R. (2008). Antibiotics residues: A global health hazard. *Veterinary.World,* 1(12): 375-377.
- Nonga, H.E., Simon, C., Karimuribo, E.D and Mdegela, R.H. (2009). Assessment of antimicrobial usage and residues in commercial chicken eggs from small holder poultry keepers in Morogoro Municipality, Tanzania. *Zoonoses and Public Health.* 57 339-344.
- NRDP, (2003). www.onlinenigeria.com>sokoto 12:20:27pm.
- Olatoye, I.O. and Ehinwomo A.A. (2009). Oxytetracycline residues in edible tissues of cattle slaughtered in Akure, Nigeria. *International Journal of Food Safety,* 11: 62-66.
- Paige, J. C. (1994). Analysis of tissue residues. *United state food and drug administration agency, animal and Veterinary section.*,9: 4-6.
- Prescott J.F., Baggot J.D. and Walker R.D. (2000): *Antimicrobial Therapy in Veterinary Medicine.* Iowa State University Press, Ames. 277 p.
- Reig and Toldra, (2007). Analytical tools for assessing the chemical safety of meat and poultry. New York Heidelberg Dordrecht London, Library of congress. 2-27.
- Roberts, M.C. (1997). Genetic mobility and distribution of tetracycline resistance determinants. In: Chadwick D.J, Goode J. (eds.), *Antibiotic Resistance: Origins, Evolution, Selection and Spread.* Wiley, Chichester (Ciba Foundation Symposium 207). 206-222.
- Segal B.M. (1963): Photosensitivity, nail discoloration and onychylosis: side effects of tetracycline therapy. *International Archives of Medicine .,* 112, 165-167.
- Shareef, A.M., Jamel Z.T. and Yonis K.M., (2009). Detection of antibiotic residues in stored poultry products. *Iraq Journal of Veterinary Science.*, 23(1): 45-48.
- Scrimshaw et al. (1954). Tetracyclines in veterinary medicine and bacterial resistance to them. *Journal of Veterinary Medicine Czech.* 49, (3): 79-100.
- Simon, A.H. and G.A. Baxter, (2006). Biosensor screening for veterinary drug residues in food stuffs. *Int. J. Animal and Vet. Advancement.* 42, 2 p.
- Smith, H.W., Tucker J.F. (1975). The effect of antibiotic therapy on the faecal excretion of *Salmonella typhimurium* by experimentally infected chickens. *Journal of Hygiene.* (Lond), 75: 275-192.
- Sirdar Mohammed M. (2008). A survey of antimicrobial residues in table

- eggs in Khartoum State, Sudan. Onderstepoort, *Journal of Veterinary Research* 79 (1) 9 p.
- Slovenian Veterinary Research (2007). Microbiological screening methods for detection of aminoglycosides, β -lactams, macrolides, tetracyclines and quinolones. University of District Columbia. 44 (1/2) 8-11.
- Snelling, C.E., Johnson R. (1952):.The value of aureomycin in prevention of cross infection in the Hospital of Sick Children. *Canadian Medical Association J.*, 66: 6-8.
- Stockstad, E.L.R., Jukes, T.H., Pierce, J., Page, A.C. and Franklin A.L. (1949). The multiple nature of animal protein factor. *J Bio. Chem.*, 180, 647-654.
- Suchayan, C., Mohammed, M.H., Mahabub, A., Sarmina, S., Saiful, B., Saifuddin, A. K. M, and Ahasanul H, MD. (2012) Antibiotic residues in milk and eggs of commercial and local farms at Chittagong, Bangladesh, *Vet. World*. 2015 April; 8(4)467
- Swann M.M. (1969). *Report of Joint Committee on the Use of Antibiotics in Animal Husbandry and Veterinary Medicine*. Her Majesty's Stationery Office, London. 27 p.
- Tollefson, L. and Miller, M. A. (2000). Antibiotic use in food animals: Controlling the human health impact. *J. Association of Official Analytical Chemists Int.*, 83: 245-256.
- Vollard, E.J. and Clasener, H.A.L. (1994). Colonization resistance. *Antimicrobial Agent Chemotherapy*, 38, 409-414. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1128/AAC.38.3.409>.
- Waksman, S. A. (1973). History of the word 'antibiotic'. *J. Historical Medical Allied Sci.* 28:284-286.
- Wambeke Van F. (2010). Validation of HPLC method of tetracycline residues in eggs and broiler meat and its application to a feeding trial. *J. Food additives and Contaminants*. 16 (2) 47-56
- WHO (2004). Residues of Veterinary Drugs without ADI/MRL- Bangkok, 24th-26th August, pp: 175.
- Zurhelle G., Petz M., Mueller-seitz E (1999) Tetracyclines and their metabolites in egg white and egg yolk. *Z. Lebensm. Unters.Forsch. J. Agric. Food Chemistry.*, 48 (12), 2000.
- Zurhelle G. (2000) Metabolites of oxytetracycline, tetracycline, and chlortetracycline and their distribution in egg white, egg yolk, and hen plasma. *J. Agric. Food Chemistry.*, 48 (12), 6392-6396